

THE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTSAL LEARNING MODEL ASSURE-BASED DESIGN ON STUDENTS OF POK FKIP UNS

Slamet Riyadi,

Rumi Iqbal Doewesⁱ

Teacher Training and Education Faculty,
Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta Indonesia

Abstract:

The research purposes were to investigate the ASSURE learning model, to test the development product, and to determine the effectiveness of ASSURE learning model on improving futsal basic skills and techniques. This research employed development research methods. The first stage was dedicated to needs analysis and used interviews method to determine the futsal learning technique problems. The second stage was dedicated to the making of products. Further evaluation products by academics and practitioners futsal, the average value is 72.38% was shown the design products can be tried out in the next stage: product testing, on a small group as many as 12 students and a large group as many as 54 students by using the questionnaire instrument. Test results for the small group were 83.19% and for large group were 84.5%. The third stage was called the effectiveness test of the product by comparing two treatment group used a pretest-posttest design. Differential value of ball feeling test in the experimental group is 54.098%, and control group is 46.269%. Differential value of dribbling test in the experimental group is 31.858%, and control group is 29.032%. Differential value of passing test in the experimental group is 98.324%, and control group is 95%. Differential value of shooting test in the experimental group is 73.810%, and control group is 68.724%. So it can be concluded that the product is effective to improve mastery of basic skills and techniques of futsal on POK FKIP UNS students.

Keywords: futsal learning model, ASSURE based design, students

ⁱ Correspondence: email doewes.rumi@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

The learning process of futsal courses at POK FKIP UNS, is not yet optimal in performing teaching functions for students. The dominant futsal learning approach carried out by drill approach. Lecturers did not yet optimal apply learning model based on scientific approach. The patterns and models of futsal learning need to make students have a more active role. ASSURE-based futsal learning is an alternative learning model that can be done to maximize the role of students in the learning process. Structured module development in according to the ASSURE model with Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) as a base in designing activity module ^[1]. The learning system design model was developed to create an effective and efficient learning activity. The steps of ASSURE design learning model through several stages such as: (1) analyze the learners' characteristic, (2) state objective, (3) select method, media and learning materials, (4) utilize materials, (5) require learner participation, and (6) evaluation and revise. Learning futsal based ASSURE design is a futsal learning model with new conception designed in accordance with need and development for students.

2. Methods

The research method was used development research approach or Research and Development (R & D). Research and development data make natural selection empirically on efforts to innovative, R & D represent only one of several inputs into process innovation ^[2].

Figure 1: Research Steps Illustration

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Overview results

No	Component	Invention
1	Introduction Stage Interview with futsal coach at POK FKIP UNS on basic futsal technique mastery of POK FKIP UNS students (n=2) with 4 points questions.	Mastery of futsal technique is not good, at POK FKIP UNS there has not been learning program specifically to teach futsal technique.
2	Developmental Stage	
	a. The evaluation results of futsal experts (n=3) with the instrument number of 20 ball feeling questions, 15 dribbling questions, 20 passing questions, 20 shooting questions.	a. The evaluation results of third futsal experts were obtained the percentage of 72.38 %, so that learning model can tried out. b. Input from the futsal experts, learning model design still required being added pictures products that are clearer and learning program design must be adjusted with the theory of learning and techniques of futsal game.
	b. Small group testing of (n=12) with the instrument number of 60 questions.	The testing result of small group was obtained the percentage of 83.19 %, so that learning model can be continued to large group testing stage.
	c. Large group testing (n=54) with the instrument number of 60 questions.	From the large group testing result was obtained the percentage of 84.5 %, so that learning model can be continued to stage of product effectiveness test.
3	Products effectiveness test	
	Different value	The different value on pretest and posttest value of products effectiveness testing: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Experimental group (n=6) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Ball feeling technique 68.4% b. Dribbling technique 77.5% c. Passing technique 50.4% d. Shooting technique 59.3% 2. Control group (n=6) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Ball feeling technique 64.2% b. Dribbling technique 75.8% c. Passing technique 47.1% d. Shooting technique 57.5%

Based on the table 1, at the introduction stage was conducted the needs analysis by interviews. The needs analysis is very important because can be find problem to solved.

Need analysis is collection of early information against difference conditions in the field and conditions intended, for problem solving ^[3]. Interview result is futsal technique not yet well in POK FKIP UNS and didn't special learning programs about the futsal technique.

Development stage was a conducted evaluation of futsal expert. Futsal expert result obtained was a percentage of 72.38%, so that learning model can tried out with expert's recommendation.

The academic advice including of (1) a kind of learning it should be noted that the learning purpose is not ambiguous; (2) the implementation procedures of futsal techniques learning with a ASSURE model more clarified; (3) the preparation of learning model need to adapt to the facilities and infrastructure in the field. Advice from the futsal practitioner including of (1) learning model made from the easy stage and increased to the difficult stage; (2) learning physical made leading to learning technique; (3) learning must be adjusted to the learning condition. Beside the experts evaluation at the development stage, also conducted product testing on small and large group.

Try out stage is the stage dedicated to know students' opinion related to the product of ASSURE learning model development. Information in the form of students' opinion obtained using questionnaires instruments with 60 questions. Small group testing was used sample of 12 students and large group used 54 students. The testing results are 83.19 % in small groups and 84.5 % in large group. This means that the product of learning model development acceptable for POK FKIP UNS students and ready done their effectiveness testing. Effectiveness testing stage objectives was determined the level of product effectiveness for formulated be a final product result, and further usage in the learning. Experimental design was used pretest and posttest design.

The experimental design was used one treatment (pretest-posttest control group design), conducted by means of the two groups given pretest to measure the initial conditions, then in the experiment given treatment, while in the control group will not give treatment. Based on a comparison of these percentages, an increase in test results of the sample group shown that the sample group was more effective than the control group.

Table 2: Data of Pre-test and Post-test result

Group	Testing	Test result		Different value	T _{count}	T _{table}	Conclusions
		Pre-test	Post-test				
Experiment group	Ball feeling	69	98	29	12,7583	2,571	Significance
	Dribbling	124	160	36	12,9455	2,571	Significance
	Passing	180	355	175	13,3243	2,571	Significance
	Shooting	245	410	165	12,9437	2,571	Significance
Control group	Ball feeling	61	94	33	12,8778	2,571	Significance
	Dribbling	113	149	36	12,4708	2,571	Significance
	Passing	160	340	180	13,2939	2,571	Significance
	Shooting	210	365	155	13,2993	2,571	Significance

Table 2 was explained the significance test of product of ASSURE learning model development. Based on the table 2, for every group is t_{count} larger than t_{table} , so can be concluded that data significance.

4. Conclusions

Based on research result and data analysis, research conclusions was that the product of ASSURE learning model development can be used as an alternative learning model to maximize the role of students in the mastery of futsal basic skills.

References

1. Bukhari, N.I.A., Omar, S., Abas, A.I.C., Shawal, B.R.M., Ibrahim, W.S.A.A.W., Hassan, A.A., Nawil, N.H.M. 2017. Exploring "Speak-O-Rama" as a Public Speaking Module: A Pilot Study in an Islamic Integrated Primary School. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*. Vol. 6 No. 2; March 2017: 249-257.
2. Gall, Meredith D., Gall Joyce P., & Borg Walter R., *Educational Research*. United States of America: Person Education, Inc., 2007.
3. Zach, T. 2011. The Effect of R&D Inputs and Outputs on the Relation between the Uncertainty of Future Operating Performance and R&D Expenditures. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*. January 2011.
4. Adams, N. E. *Bloom's Taxonomy of Cognitive Learning Objectives*. J Med Lib Assoc 103(3) July 2015. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3163/1536-5050.103.3.010>.
5. Atwi M. Suparman. 2014. *Desain Intruksional Modern*. Jakarta: Erlangga.

6. Bai, Y., and Chi, A. *The Feasibility of the Develop of Futsal in Primary and Middle Schools*.
7. *2016 2nd International Conference on Modern Education and Social Science (MESS 2016)*. ISBN: 978-1-60595-346-5: 771-775.
8. Beato, M., Coratella, G., Schena, F., Hulton, A. T. 2017. *Evaluation Of The External And Internal Workload In Female Futsal Players*. *Biol. Sport* 2017; 34: 227-231.
9. Benny A. Pribadi. 2011. *Model ASSURE untuk Mendesain Pembelajaran Sukses*. Jakarta: Dian Rakyat.
10. _____. 2009. *Model Desain Sistem Pembelajaran*. Jakarta: Dian Rakyat.
11. Bukhari, N.I.A., Omar, S., Abas, A.I.C., Shawal, B.R.M., Ibrahim, W.S.A.A.W., Hassan, A.A., Nawi, N.H.M. 2017. Exploring "Speak-O-Rama" as a Public Speaking Module: A Pilot Study in an Islamic Integrated Primary School. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*. ISSN 2200-3592 (Print), ISSN 2200-3452 (Online). Vol. 6 No. 2; March 2017: 249-257.
13. Costa, L. C. A., Nascimento, J. V., and Vieira, L. F. 2016. *Teaching Invasive Team Sports In The School Environment: From Theory To Practice From The Perspective Of A Hybrid Model*. *J. Phys. Educ.* v. 27, e2709, 2016. DOI: 10.4025/jphyseduc.v27i1.2709: 1-14.
14. Flôres, F. S., Menezes, K. M., and Katzer, J. I. *Influences of Gender on Attention and Learning of Motor Skills*. *J. Phys. Educ.* v. 27, e2706, 2016. DOI: 10.4025/jphyseduc.v27i1.2706: 1-9.
15. Gall, Meredith D., Gall Joyce P., & Borg Walter R., *Educational Research*. United States of America: Person Education, Inc., 2007.
16. Hidayatullah, M. F. 2006. *Mendidik Anak Dengan Bermain*. UNS Press, Surakarta.
17. Hermans, V., and Engler, R. 2011. *Futsal: Technique Tactics Training*. Meyer and Meyer Sport, UK.
18. Jakiwa, J., Geok, S. K., Fauzee, M. S. O. 2015. Impact of Self-Talk among University Futsal Player in University of Putra Malaysia: A Qualitative Approach. *South-East Asian Journal for Youth, Sports & Health Education*, 1(1) April 2015. ISSN 2407-7348: 1-8.
19. Kacem, N., Guemri, A., Naffeti, C., and Elloumi, A. 2016. Mechanism of Social Reproduction of the Culture Futsal: Modelling of the Universals of Futsal and Sense of the Rules of the Game: Analysis of Shooting at the European Cup Matches. *Physical Education*, 2016, 6, 59-66.

20. Karavelioglu, M. B., Harmanci, H., Kaya, M., and Erol, M. 2016. *Effects of Plyometric Training on Anaerobic Capacity and Motor Skills in Female Futsal Players*. *Anthropologist*, 23(30): 355-360.
21. Kartal, R. Comparison of Speed, Agility, Anaerobic Strength and Anthropometric Characteristics in Male Football and Futsal Players. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*. Vol. 4, No. 7; July 2016. ISSN 2324-805X E-ISSN 2324-8068: 47-53.
22. Keshvari, B., and Senner, V. 2015. *Comparison of Shoe-Surface Traction on Various Playing Surfaces in Futsal*. *Procedia Engineering* 112 (2015) 267-272.
23. [23] Kocić, M., Joksimović, A., and Stevanović, M. 2016. Differences In Explosive Strength Of Legs Between Football And Futsal Players. *Physical Education and Sport* Vol. 14, No 2, 2016, pp. 269-278.
24. Li, J., Schiller, D., Schoenbaum, G., Phelps, E. A., and Daw, N. D. 2012. *Differential Roles of Human Striatum and Amygdala in Associative Learning*. *Nat Neurosci.* ; 14(10): 1250–1252. doi:10.1038/nn.2904.
25. Ridderinkhof, Richard K., and Brass, M. 2015. How Kinaesthetic Motor Imagery Works: A Predictive-Processing Theory Of Visualization In Sports And Motor Expertise. *Journal of Physiology - Paris* 109 (2015) 53–63.
26. Rosa, J.P.O.D., and Vital, R.A.D. The Use of Facebook in Argumentative Writing: Towards an Instructional Design Model. *AsTEN Journal of Teacher Education* 2016. Volume 1, Issue No. 2: 39-58.
27. Sarmiento, H., Bradley, P. S., Anguera, M. T., Campanico, J. 2015. Quantifying the Offensive Sequences that Result in Goals in Elite Futsal Matches. *Journal of Sports Sciences*. July 2015. DOI: 10.1080/02640414.2015.1066024.
28. Sharon E. Smaldino, Deborah L. Lowther, & James D. Russell. 2014. *Instructional Technology & Media for learning* terjemahan. Jakarta: Kencana Prenadamedia Group.
29. Sezer, B., Yilmaz, F.G.K., Yilmaz, R. 2013. Integrating Technology Into Classroom: The Learner-Centered Instructional Design. *International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications*. October 2013 Volume: 4 Issue: 4 Article: 12 ISSN 1309-6249: 134-
30. Snow, Nicholas J., Mang, Cameron S., Roig, M., McDonnell, Michelle N., Campbell, Kristin L., and Boyd, Lara A. 2016. The Effect of an Acute Bout of Moderate-Intensity Aerobic Exercise on Motor Learning of a Continuous Tracking Task. *Journal.pone.0150039* (2016): 1-16.

31. Sterdt, E., Liersch, S., and Walter, U. 2013. Correlates Of Physical Activity Of Children And Adolescents: A Systematic Review Of Reviews. *Health Education Journal*, 0(0) 1–18.
32. Sugiyono. *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan: Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R & D*. Bandung: Alfabet, 2015.
33. Jay D Goldstein, & Seppo E Iso-Ahola.(2006). Promotion sportsmanship in youth sports (*Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*)
34. Vieira, L. H. P., Doğramaci, S. N., Barbieri, R. A., Moura, F. A., Andrade, V. L., Cesar, G. M., and Santiago, P. R. P. 2016. *Preliminary Results on Organization On The Court, Physical And Technical Performance Of Brazilian Professional Futsal Players: Comparison Between Friendly Pre-Season And Official Match*. Motriz, Rio Claro, v.22 n.2, p. 80-92, Apr./June 2016.
35. Zach, T. 2011. The Effect of R&D Inputs and Outputs on the Relation between the Uncertainty of Future Operating Performance and R&D Expenditures. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*. January 2011. DOI: 10.1177/0148558X11400583: 1-43.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).